

Deliverable D9.3: Project Management Plan - 2

Deliverable information

Related Work Package	WP9
Type of document	R
Dissemination Level	PU
Deliverable Lead	Proplast
Contractual delivery date	31/07/2025
Actual submission date	
Author(s)	Proplast

Revision and history chart

Version	Date	Main author	Summary of changes
1.0	31/07/2025	Proplast	

Project description

Today 2.5 million tonnes of composite material are in use in the wind energy sector globally. Wind turbine blades are made up of composite materials that allow lighter and longer blades with optimised aerodynamic shape, which boost the performance of wind energy. However, current wind blade composites exhibit relatively short life spans, are problematic to repair and are notoriously difficult to recycle. As we continue to build more wind farms these issues pose a major problem to achieving a truly sustainable European wind energy sector.

EOLIAN project will develop an innovative new smart wind turbine blade, manufactured from a recyclable circular platform chemistry (vitrimers) and basal fibres, with sensors and heating actuators that detect damage early before it becomes a major issue. In the project, we will validate these performance claims through the manufacture, testing and benchmarking of a smart sensor-assisted vitrimer-based composite 14m prototyped wind blade. Additionally, we will prove circular recyclability through the manufacture of 2nd generation composites with recycled fibers and recycled vitrimer obtained after the chemical recycling by vacuum infusion and with composite parts produced by SMC following mechanical recycling.

Table of content

Abbreviations and acronyms.....	5
1 Introduction.....	6
2 Organization, governance and decision making	6
2.1.1 General Assembly.....	6
2.1.2 Project Management Board	7
2.1.3 Coordinator	7
2.1.4 Work Package Leaders.....	8
2.2 Organization meetings and procedures	8
2.2.1 Frequency of consortium meetings	8
2.2.2 Notice of meetings	9
2.2.3 Sending the agenda	9
2.2.4 Adding agenda items	9
2.2.5 Decisions.....	9
3 Communication strategy	10
3.1 Internal	10
3.1.1 EOLIAN OneDrive share folder	10
3.1.2 Partners contact list	10
3.1.3 Teleconferencing	10
3.1.4 Meetings	10
3.1.5 Absences.....	10
3.2 External communication and dissemination	10
3.2.1 Dissemination strategy	10
4 Procedure for technical monitoring.....	11
4.1 Project management plan excel file	11
4.2 System Design Readiness Reviews	11
4.2.1 Preliminary Design Review (PDR).....	12
5 Procedure for deliverables preparation	13
5.1 Structure of deliverables.....	13
5.2 Tracking of deliverables and review process	13
5.3 Dissemination level of deliverables	14
6 Documents management.....	14
6.1 Storage.....	14
6.2 Document templates	15
7 Procedure for technical review report preparation.....	15
8 Financial management.....	15

8.1	Procedure for financial monitoring	15
8.2	Procedure for the internal financial reporting period	15
8.3	Mandatory financial reporting period.....	16
8.4	Keeping Records.....	16
8.5	Payment handling.....	16
8.5.1	Pre-financing.....	16
-	Interim Payments.....	16
-	Final Payment.....	17
-	Guarantee Fund.....	17
8.5.2	Distribution of funds to partners	17
9	Risk Management Documentation.....	17
9.1	Risk management and risk register	17
10	Conclusions	18
11	List of Annex.....	18

Abbreviations and acronyms

Abbreviation / Acronym	Description
WP	Work Package
EU	European Union
EC	European Commission
INEA	Innovation & Networks Executive Agency, an agency of the European Commission
HE	Horizon Europe – the Framework Programme for Research and Innovation (2021-2027)
CFS	Certificate of the Financial Statement
VAT	Value Added Tax (a sales tax)
TBC	To be confirmed
GA	Grant Agreement
PMP	Project Management Plan
PMB	Project Management Board
EEAB	External Expert Advisory board

Project coordinator		
1	PROP	Proplast - Consorzio per la promozione della cultura plastica
Project beneficiaries		
2	POLM	Politecnico di Milano
3	ZOREN	Zrl enerji elektrik uretim as
4	IRES	Ires - innovation in research and engineering solutions
5	NORV	Norvento tecnologia, s.l.
5,1	NNF	Norvento ned factory, s.l.u. (<i>affiliate partner to Norv</i>)
6	TEK	Fundacion Tekniker
7	EuCIA	Association Europeenne de l'industrie des Composites
8	AEP	Aep polymers srl
Project associated partners		
9	BUL	Brunel University London
10	ENT	Entelea limited

1 Introduction

This Project Management Plan presented on October 2024, represented the first version with the general information about the processes, procedures, roles and obligations of each partner for the consortium members of the EOLIAN project. The processes and procedures have been described defining methodology in order to ensure the efficiency of the project.

The Project Management Plan 2 regards the PMP updated with the information related to the last 12 month of the project and contains the data collected by the coordinator and the partners.

The aim of this document is to demonstrate if the guidelines and procedures have been performed and achieved by the partnership and, in any case, if these procedures worked correctly.

As the previous PMP, this updated plan is based on several key documents/meetings including:

- The EOLIAN Consortium Agreement – based on the DESCA - DESCA – Model Consortium Agreement for Horizon Europe, version 1.1, November 2022 (www.DESCA-2020.eu)
- The EOLIAN Grant Agreement – GA Number 101147532

2 Organization, governance and decision making

As in the previous PMP, the organisational structure of the consortium shall comprise the following Consortium Bodies and these have not been changed:

- The **General Assembly**, as the ultimate decision-making body of the consortium.
- The **Project Management Board** as the supervisory body for the execution of the Project, which shall report to and be accountable to the General Assembly.
- The **Coordinator** as the legal entity acting as the intermediary between the Parties and the Granting Authority. The Coordinator shall, in addition to its responsibilities as a Party, perform the tasks assigned to it as described in the Grant Agreement and this Consortium Agreement.
- **External Expert Advisory board.**

2.1.1 General Assembly

In the following table, we will show the schedule of the General Assembly meetings organized in the last 12 months:

General assembly	Date	Where
Kick-off meeting	12-13 June 2024	Proplast – Alessandria (IT)
General Assembly M6	4-5 December 2024	Brunel Composite Centre – Cambridge (UK)
General Assembly M12	16-17 June 2025	Tekniker – Eibar (SP)

In each project meeting, one designated representative from each partner organization has actively participated, ensuring balanced and consistent representation across the consortium (see Annex 1 for details).

Comprehensive minutes of all meetings have been systematically prepared and are available for consultation in the Project Shared Folder. These documents serve as a transparent record of discussions, decisions, and action points agreed upon during the meetings.

Throughout the course of these meetings, no significant issues or sources of dissatisfaction have been reported. The collaborative atmosphere and constructive engagement of all partners have contributed to an effective coordination process.

2.1.2 Project Management Board

The Project Management Board has organized different meetings within the Coordinator and the representatives of the Parties appointed to it by the General Assembly.

The meeting organized are the following:

Project Management Board	Date	Where
Project Management Board-1	16/09/2024	Online meeting
Project Management Board-2	05/12/2024	Brunel University – Cambridge (UK)
Project Management Board-3	25/02/2025	Online meeting
Project Management Board-4	17/06/2025	Tekniker – Eibar (SP)

The new list of representatives of each partner is:

	Organisation	Assigned representatives
1	PROP	Marco Monti, (Susana Remotti)
2	POLM	Marco Luigi Longana, (Claudia Marano)
3	ZOREN	Zeynep Korkmaz, (Nilgun Kurtcu)
4	IRES	Foteini Petrakli, (Elias Koumoulos)
5	NORV	Xabier Munduate Echarri, (Claudia Vázquez Sanz)
5,1	NNF	Xabier Munduate Echarri, (Claudia Vázquez Sanz)
6	TEK	Miren Blanco, (Cristina Monteserin)
7	EuCIA	Raphael Pleynet, (Amanda Jacob)
8	AEP	Andrea Minigher, (Walter Pitacco)
9	BUL	Daniel Paul, (Nithin Amirth Jayasree)
10	ENT	Dimitrios Anastasiou, (Kostas Papadopoulos)

2.1.3 Coordinator

The Coordinator shall be the intermediary between the Parties and the Granting Authority and shall perform all tasks assigned to it as described in the Grant Agreement and in this Consortium Agreement.

In particular, the Coordinator shall be responsible for:

- monitoring compliance by the Parties with their obligations under this Consortium Agreement and the Grant Agreement
- keeping the address list of Members and other contact persons updated and available
- collecting, reviewing to verify consistency and submitting reports, other deliverables (including financial statements and related certifications) and specific requested documents to the Granting Authority

- transmitting documents and information connected with the Project to any other Parties concerned
- administering the financial contribution of the Granting Authority and fulfilling the financial tasks
- providing, upon request, the Parties with official copies or originals of documents that are in the sole possession of the Coordinator when such copies or originals are necessary for the Parties to present claims.
- Calling all the meeting, proposing the decisions and preparing the agenda of the General Assembly meetings, presiding over the meetings, preparing the minutes of the meetings and monitoring the implementation of the decisions taken during the meetings.

If one or more of the Parties is late in submission of any Project deliverable, the Coordinator may nevertheless submit the other 'Parties' Project deliverables and all other documents required by the Grant Agreement to the Granting Authority in time.

2.1.4 Work Package Leaders

In the following table the representatives of each partner, that is work package leader is reported.

WP	Assigned leader	Assigned leader
1	Norvento	Xabier Munduate Echarri
2	Tekniker	Cristina Monteserín
3	POLIMI	Marco Luigi Longana
4	Tekniker	Alazne Martinez
5	AEP	Andrea Minigher
6	Proplast	Ilaria Poncini
7	IRES	Foteini Petrakli
8	EuCIA	Amanda Jacob
9	Proplast	Marco Monti

8

2.2 Organization meetings and procedures

2.2.1 Frequency of consortium meetings

The constituted meeting frequencies for the General Assembly and Executive board are detailed below:

	Ordinary meeting	Extraordinary meeting
General Assembly	At least once a year	At any time upon request of the Project Management Board or 1/3 of the Members of the General Assembly
Project Management Board	At least quarterly	At any time upon the request of any Member of the Project Management Board

The General Assembly and the Project Management Board have been regularly organized, and the frequency has been respected. The dates are detailed in Point 2.1.1 and 2.1.2.

2.2.2 Notice of meetings

The chairperson of a Consortium Body shall give written notice of a meeting to each Member of that Consortium Body as soon as possible and no later than the minimum number of days preceding the meeting as indicated below.

	Ordinary meeting	Extraordinary meeting
General Assembly	45 calendar days	15 calendar days
Project Management Board	14 calendar days	7 calendar days

The procedure was implemented and adhered to throughout the first 12 months of the project.

2.2.3 Sending the agenda

The chairperson of a Consortium Body shall prepare and send each Member of that Consortium Body an agenda no later than the minimum number of days preceding the meeting as indicated below.

General Assembly	21 calendar days, 10 calendar days for an extraordinary meeting
Project Management Board	7 calendar days

The procedure was implemented and adhered to throughout the first 12 months of the project.

9

2.2.4 Adding agenda items

Any agenda item requiring a decision by the Members of a Consortium Body must be identified as such on the agenda.

Any Member of a Consortium Body may add an item to the original agenda by written notice to all the other Members of that Consortium Body up to the minimum number of days preceding the meeting as indicated below.

General Assembly	14 calendar days, 7 calendar days for an extraordinary meeting
Project Management Board	2 calendar days

During a meeting the Members of a Consortium Body present or represented can unanimously agree to add a new item to the original agenda.

The procedure was implemented and adhered to throughout the first 12 months of the project.

2.2.5 Decisions

Any decision may also be taken without a meeting if

- a) the Coordinator circulates to all Members of the General Assembly a suggested decision with a deadline for responses of at least 10 calendar days after receipt by a Party and
- b) the decision is agreed by 51 % of all Parties.

The Coordinator shall inform all the Parties of the outcome of the vote. A veto may be submitted up to 15 calendar days after receipt of this information. The decision will be binding after the Coordinator sends a notification to all Members. The Coordinator will keep records of the votes and make them available to the Parties on request.

The procedure was implemented and adhered to throughout the first 12 months of the project.

3 Communication strategy

3.1 Internal

3.1.1 EOLIAN OneDrive share folder

A Microsoft Teams repository has been created by the Coordinator, where all the documents are available at any time to the Consortium members.

3.1.2 Partners contact list

A partner contact list has been created by the Coordinator as an excel file and shared by the repository. It is going to be updated upon request of the partners.

3.1.3 Teleconferencing

Microsoft Teams has been used for telcos throughout the duration of the project as recommended in the PMP.

3.1.4 Meetings

Prior to a meeting or telephone conference a calling notice have been issued, setting the time and date of the meeting, identifying the attendees and objectives of the meeting, the agenda and reference to any supporting documentation.

During physical meeting the calling notice has been included the meeting location, and recommended travel arrangement and accommodation.

For work package meetings, the agenda has been issued in time before the meeting and any changes to the agenda have been sent at least 7 days before the meeting.

The minutes of the meeting and a draft of the minutes were available 14 days after the end of the meeting. They circulated to all parties concerned for comments or approval, upon issuing the minutes a deadline settled for the return of comments. The same procedure has been implemented for the minutes from the work package.

3.1.5 Absences

During the first 12 months of the project, no member of the Executive Board, work package leader or task leader expects have been absent from work or unable fulfil their duties for a significant period.

3.2 External communication and dissemination

3.2.1 Dissemination strategy

The dissemination strategy has the purpose to ensure that the results from the EOLIAN project are disseminated to end-users and researchers, ensuring the implementation of the products from this project and that any future or on-going research builds upon and does not duplicate the work of the EOLIAN project.

The dissemination of the project outcomes and any publications have been planned in the specific Deliverable 8.1 Plan for dissemination & exploitation, incl. communication activities.

4 Procedure for technical monitoring

4.1 Project management plan excel file

An excel file has been created as a valuable tool for the project management plan. It highlights the most important information and is divided in different spreadsheets, as follows.

Project overview. It reports the most important information about the project, e.g. title and acronym, GA number, starting date, duration, partner list.

WP. It reports the list of WPs and Tasks, with WP leaders and participants.

GANTT. It reports the GANTT chart of the project with two more columns where to report the eventual shift.

Deliverable. It reports the list of the deliverables, with the related WP, the responsible of the preparation, the dissemination level, the type of deliverable, the planned delivery date. There is also a last column with the potential shift needed, to be used only in the case the partner responsible highlight it in due time.

Milestone. It reports the list of the milestones, with the related WP, the responsible of the attainment, the planned date. There is also a last column with the potential shift needed, to be used only in the case the partner responsible highlight it in due time.

Project timeline and deadlines. It helps the monitoring of the deadlines. The last spreadsheets are related to project activities and will be used to record information regarding specific technical activities and for the risk management. These spreadsheets will be updated during the project implementation. They are:

Action tracker. It reports information regarding specific key actions.

Risk Management. It reports the detailed list of the risks which come out during the project activities (more details are reported in Section 9 of this Deliverable).

Risk Guidance. It reports a guide about how to rate the presented risks.

The excel file is under the control of the management team of the coordinator, and it can be available to the project officer upon request, at any time.

4.2 System Design Readiness Reviews

System Design Readiness Reviews will provide an in-depth assessment that the resulting design/concept is realistic and attainable from a programmatic and technical sense. There are three technical readiness reviews planned during the course of the project.

The first two reviews comprise the Preliminary Design Review (PDR) at the end of M18 of the project and the Critical Design Review (CDR) scheduled on M27. During those design reviews, an

assessment is made on whether the maturity of the design is appropriate to support proceeding to the next phase of the works. Each time the assessment will be made based on a set of criteria imposed by the project management board. At the end of each design review, a detailed technical report will be issued describing the TRL achieved, the technical assessment on the reviewed configurations and the schedule for the next period.

4.2.1 Preliminary Design Review (PDR)

The Preliminary Design Review (PDR), which was planned to be finished by the end of M18, was actually concluded by July 2025 (M14), after the following steps:

1. Proplast prepared an excel file to be filled by the partners for creating the specification list and sent it to the partners (16/1/2025).
2. Proplast assembled the received contributions and the KPI of the project to set up the final version of the "specification file", which appears as follows (the updated version is available as external excel file) (26/2/2025):

TYPE	APPLICATION	SPECIFICATION (PDR)	PROP	POLM	TEK	AEP	Required by
Preference	Full blade	biobased content of the vanillin polyimine vitrimer >60%	x		x	x	Project KPI
Requirement	Full blade	Viscosity of the reactive mixture ≈ 250 cP, considering vacuum infusion as a processing technique	x		x	x	Project KPI
Preference	Full blade	mechanical strength of the vitrimer >98% with respect to the one of traditional thermoset systems for wind blades	x		x	x	Project KPI
Requirement	Full blade	Resin onset Tg must be higher than 65°C according to standard GL2010	x		x	x	NORV
Requirement	Full blade	Pot life 100g/RT must be in the range of 80 minutes	x		x	x	NORV
Requirement	Full blade	Use of lower toxicity solvents (avoid GHS06 and GHS08 at least)	x		x	x	AEP
Preference	Full blade	Solid content of the reaction mixture >10% to increase productivity	x		x	x	AEP
Requirement	Blade component	Minimum quantity of 300 l of vitrimer				x	NORV
Requirement	Full blade	Minimum quantity of 1200 l of vitrimer				x	NORV
Preference	Full blade	Solid content of the reaction mixture >10% to increase productivity	x		x	x	AEP
Preference	Full blade	mechanical strength and stiffness of the composites >98% with respect to the one of traditional composites for wind blades		x			Project KPI
Preference	Sample	mechanical strength of the composites after reparation >95% with respect to the one before damage (reparability)		x			Project KPI
Preference	Full blade	Bio and natural content of the composites (summing vitrimer biobased content and mineral natural fibres) >80wt%		x			Project KPI
Preference	Sample	formable angle after heating of the composites (from wrinkle-free flat panels to L-shaped panels without delamination) (reusability) >30°		x			Project KPI
Preference	Sample	mechanical strength of fibres after chemical recycling > 95% with respect to the one of virgin		x	x		Project KPI
Preference	Sample	percentage of vitrimer recovered by chemical recycling > 70%	x		x	x	Project KPI
Preference	Sample	mechanical strength of part obtained after mechanical recycling > 90%with respect to the one of original composite		x			Project KPI
Requirement	Blade component	Lightning strike resistance evaluated (by conductivity tests)			x		NORV
Requirement	Full blade	Basalt fibres sizing compatible with epoxy resins systems, as well as with the newly developed vitrimer resin so that the infusion process is not influenced by that.		x			NORV
Requirement	Full blade	Erosion resistance evaluated		x	x		NORV
Preference	Blade component	Mechanical strength and stiffness of 2nd generation composites >90%with respect to the one of 1st generation vitrimer-based composite using materials obtained after chemical recycling	x	x	x		Project KPI
Preference	Blade component	Mechanical strength and stiffness of 2nd generation composites >70%with respect to the one of 1st generation vitrimer-based composite using materials obtained after mechanical recycling	x	x	x		Project KPI
Preference	Full blade	GWP Reduction > 10%	x	x	x	x	Project KPI
Preference	Full blade	Sensorics and erosion detection accuracy > 80%			x		Project KPI

3. An online meeting was held on 28th March to finalize the file and to prepare the PDR meeting in Spain
4. A "specification leader" was appointed (and marked in blue in the excel file, as shown in the table above)
5. Every specification leader prepared one slide to explain, for that specification, whether a) Eolian already get to the results; b) Eolian reached the result at a certain level and are likely

to reach 100% before the end of the project with the described actions; c) this specification cannot be reached but we have a backup plan.

6. A PDR meeting was held in Tekniker, on 16th June 2025.

During the PDR meeting, a thorough discussion was held on every specification. The slides are available and can be considered as the minutes of the meeting, together with a pdf report, where specific conclusions are reported. These documents are in the repository of the project and can be made available to the project officer whenever it wishes to check them.

This tool can be considered an assessment on whether the maturity of the design is appropriate to support proceeding to the next phase of the works.

5 Procedure for deliverables preparation

5.1 Structure of deliverables

Each deliverable followed a set structure as set out in the templates of:

- Deliverable information
- Revision and history chart
- Project description
- Table of Contents
- Abbreviations and Acronyms
- Introduction of the objectives of the deliverable
- Main body of the report – this section will explain the task that was carried out and the results generated and illustrate the technical and scientific progress made within the task.
- Conclusions – these sections should be a summary of the major outputs of the deliverable and the implications of the results on other parts of the project or the impact on that the results will have for the end-users and the railway community. The conclusions should also highlight the deficiencies in the work carried out and where future improvements or further work should be directed.
- References, if any
- Annexes – Annexes of data or further information not suitable for the main body of the report either due to its detailed nature or separated for confidentiality purposes (if any).

13

5.2 Tracking of deliverables and review process

A specific procedure has been set up for the deliverable preparation timeline, to guarantee the compliance with the planned deadline. The use of a dedicated spreadsheet, which describes all the deliverables, their submission dates with the corresponding project month and each deliverable responsible was very helpful for the coordination of this task. In fact, all deliverables were submitted on time.

The Coordinator for each deliverable, 60 days before its deadline, sent a remind message to the deliverable responsible partner. The deliverables drafts have been delivered to the Coordinator, as decided in the previous version of this document, 15 days before the submission date. After the revision, and in some cases with requested adjustments, the Coordinator uploaded on the dedicated platform all the deliverables before the due date.

The deliverable 9.1 was rejected by the PO on October 10th, 2024. After revisions it was re-upload on October 15th, 2024, and approved on November 18th, 2024.

The deliverable 1.1 was rejected on November 18th, 2024. An improved version of the document has been uploaded by the Coordinator on November 21st, 2024, and approved on November 26th, 2024.

The deliverables uploaded are the following:

WP	Deliverable	Due Date	Delivery	Dissemination level	Approval Date
WP9	D9.1	31 Jul 2024	15 Oct 2024	PU	18 Nov 2024
WP1	D1.1	30 Sep 2024	21 Nov 2024	SEN	26 Nov 2024
WP8	D8.1	30 Nov 2024	29 Nov 2024	SEN	Approval pending
WP8	D8.2	30 Nov 2024	29 Nov 2024	PU	Approval pending
WP9	D9.2	30 Nov 2024	27 Nov 2024	PU	Approval pending
WP8	D8.3	28 Feb 2025	27 Feb 2025	PU	Approval pending
WP2	D2.1	31 May 2025	29 May 2025	SEN	Approval pending
WP3	D3.1	30 Jun 2025	30 Jun 2025	SEN	Approval pending

5.3 Dissemination level of deliverables

During the proposal stage it was agreed that most of the EOLIAN deliverables would have a public dissemination level meaning that they will be made available to anyone, and this is to ensure that the results of the project can reach the largest audience possible.

On the project website was created a dedicated webpage (<https://eolian-project.eu/publications/>) in which, the responsible partner Eucia, uploaded the deliverable 9.1, the only public deliverable approved for the moment.

A Zenodo community was created "EOLIAN Project" (<https://zenodo.org/communities/eolian-project/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest>) and D9.1 was uploaded.

6 Documents management

It is expected that over the course of the EOLIAN project that many documents will be produced, it is therefore vital that document management processes are followed in order to enable users to locate and identify relevant files and to ensure version control.

6.1 Storage

In these 12 months of the project, all documents produced in the project have been stored and archived on the extranet site (Microsoft Teams repository), with a folder for each work package including the WP9 Project Management and additional folders for General Documents, Meetings and Administrative documents. The definitive versions of the Deliverables have been uploaded in a specific folder of the General section: Working reports have been uploaded in the WP folders, as well as the documents related to meetings in the Meeting folders.

The procedure was implemented and will be maintained throughout the remainder of the project.

6.2 Document templates

Document templates have been prepared which use a standard format including defined styles, page layout and content structure. These templates have been prepared by the Project Management Team are available on the extranet site under General Documents/Templates.

Templates produced are used for the following documents:

- Deliverables (MS Word format)
- Meeting Calling Notices (MS Word format)
- Meeting Minutes (MS Word format)
- Presentations (MS Powerpoint format)

7 Procedure for technical review report preparation

According to the release of the first version of this document, the subsequent technical reports are scheduled to be prepared at Months 14, 28, 42 of the project deadlines.

In alignment with the agreements established during the last General Assembly held in Eibar at M12, and in accordance with the defined procedure — which stipulates the initiation of the reporting process 90 days before the submission deadline — the preparation of the next technical report will start on June 30th, 2025. This report is due for submission to the EU portal by September 30th, 2025.

Each Work Package (WP) Leader is responsible for compiling and submitting their respective draft contributions to the Coordinator by August 30th, 2025. This timeline allows the Coordinator sufficient time to conduct a thorough review of the report, addressing both technical accuracy and formal consistency.

Throughout the month of September 2025, the Coordinator will finalize the revisions, ensuring that the complete and consolidated technical report is ready for timely submission to the EU portal by the end of the reporting period.

8 Financial management

8.1 Procedure for financial monitoring

The specific procedure that has been set up for the financial monitoring to guarantee the compliance with the deadline establish in the Grant Agreement has been followed without running into any blocking problems.

8.2 Procedure for the internal financial reporting period

The Coordinator, as decided, required to all beneficiaries an internal financial report at month 7, uploading the files required in the dedicated share folder.

The procedure has been regularly completed as follows:

- the Coordinator sent a reminding message and uploaded the common file excel to be completed in the share folder 15 days before the end of the period;
- the partners have completed the excel file in time and within 20 days of the end of the period.

The next internal progress report will be prepared on month 14th and it will be mandatory and part of the financial statement to be completed in the Findings and Tenders Platform.

8.3 Mandatory financial reporting period

The financial report has not been prepared yet. In the General Assembly M12 in Eibar, the Coordinator invited to the partners to complete individually the financial report by 30-day after the end of the period in order to check and approve the expenditures.

8.4 Keeping Records

Records and supporting documentation generated during the project must be kept for five years after the payment of the balance as required in the article 20 of the Grant Agreement. See the GA for detailed information.

The procedure has been implemented, and the partners are sharing the documents in the common share folder.

8.5 Payment handling

The maximum total EC financial contribution for EOLIAN is fixed at 3'653'176.25€.

8.5.1 Pre-financing.

The pre-finance payment made to the co-ordinator was 52.50% of the Maximum EC Financial Contribution less the 5% contribution the guarantee fund. This translates into pre-financing of 1'918'240.77€. Of this 1'735'581.96€ was transferred to the consortium (coordinator) and 182'658.81€ kept by the Commission for the Guarantee Fund.

The Coordinator made payments on June 11th, 2024. In the table below the amount paid to each partner:

Initial pre-financing payment			
1	PROP	Proplast - Consorzio per la promozione della cultura plastica	259.338,93
2	POLM	Politecnico di Milano	237.544,24
3	ZOREN	Zrl enerji elektrik uretim as	94.126,91
4	IRES	Ires - innovation in research and engineering solutions	166.815,44
5	NORV	Norvento tecnologia, s.l.	263.624,22
5,1	NNF	Norvento ned factory, s.l.u. (affiliate partner to norv)	153.216,04
6	TEK	Fundacion Tekniker	324.797,21
7	EuCIA	Association Europeenne de l'industrie des Composites	128.867,75
8	AEP	Aep Polymers srl	107.251,22
			1.735.581,96

- Interim Payments.

No interim payment has been made yet.

- Final Payment.

No final payment has been made yet.

- Guarantee Fund

See Point 8.5.1.

8.5.2 Distribution of funds to partners

The EC financial contribution has been received on May 31st, 2024, and regularly distributed on June 11th, 2024, by the Project Coordinator.

9 Risk Management Documentation

The Issue Register is collecting and organizing any issue as it arises, these ones is going to be analysed and escalated or dealt with accordingly. Work Package Leader are registering the deviations from the project plan, identification of new risks or just concerns.

In the previous deliverable, it was established the role of the Project Manager as organizer of the actions to items raised on the Issue Register and controller of the actions to follow up. However, it is the role of all consortium members, third parties and User Group members to raise issues and present them to the Project Manager.

9.1 Risk management and risk register

A list of risks was identified during the grant preparation stage and reviewed at the kick-off meeting. Each WP leader is updating the risk register and identifying new ones.

Each risk is continuous assessed by the Project Management Board for its criticality to the overall plan of work and normal risk assessment techniques such as a likelihood/severity matrix can be used for assessing the potential risk impact and therefore the requirement for the implementation of a contingency plan.

The PMP excel file, which has been described in Section 4 and that reports also the risk management, is under the control of the management team of the coordinator, and it can be available to the project officer upon request, at any time.

The risk register is going to be reviewed by the Project Management Board at each board meeting, any new risks identified updated, assessed and contingency plans created if necessary. The Executive Board will also assess whether the likelihood or severity of existing risks have changed and create or updated the contingency plans. If a contingency plan results in a change to GA Annex 1 a proposal for the change should be proposed by the Project Management Board for approval by the General Assembly.

10 Conclusions

The project management plan presented in the document provides the results of the first 12 months of the project produced by the Project Management Team and the consortium partners.

This document demonstrates that the procedure of the Project Management Plan - 1 has been efficiently and well managed by the Coordinator and the partners.

If any item in this document is ambiguous, or further assistance or advise is required then please contact the Project Management Team:

Marco Monti
marco.monti@proplast.it
Technical coordinator

Susana Remotti
susana.remotti@proplast.it
Financial coordinator

Sonia Gandini
sonia.gandini@proplast.it
Financial coordinator

Proplast, Via Roberto di Ferro n. 86, 15122 Alessandria, Italy

11 List of Annex

Annex 1: Signatures of the in-person participants

Kick-off Meeting

12th June 2024

Proplast

Participant list

Name	Surname	Company	Signature
Miren	Blanco	Tekniker	
Alazne	Martinez	Tekniker	
Cristina	Monteserin	Tekniker	
Mando	Kostapanou	IRES	
Georgios	Kourouklidis	IRES	
Zeynep	Korkmaz	Zorlu Enerji	
Tuğrul	Hazar	Zorlu Enerji	
Claudia	Vázquez Sanz	Norvento Enerxía	
Marco Luigi	Longana	PoliMi	
Claudia	Marano	PoliMi	
Roberto	Frassine	PoliMi/EuCIA	
Dimitrios	Fakis	Brunel Composites Centre	
Nithin	Amirth Jayasree	Brunel Composites Centre	
Dimitris	Anastasiou	ENTELEA LTD	
Andrea	Minigher	AEP Polymers s.r.l.	
Marco	Monti	Proplast	
Ilaria	Poncini	Proplast	
Sonia	Gandini	Proplast	
Susana	Remotti	Proplast	
Marta	Zaccone	Proplast	

Kick-off Meeting

13th June 2024

Proplast

Participant list

Name	Surname	Company	Signature
Miren	Blanco	Tekniker	
Alazne	Martinez	Tekniker	
Cristina	Monteserin	Tekniker	
Mando	Kostapanou	IRES	
Georgios	Kourouklidis	IRES	
Zeynep	Korkmaz	Zortu Enerji	
Tuğrul	Hazar	Zortu Enerji	
Claudia	Vázquez Sanz	Norvento Enerxía	
Marco Luigi	Longana	PoliMi	
Claudia	Marano	PoliMi	
Roberto	Frassine	PoliMi/EuCIA	
Dimitrios	Fakis	Brunel Composites Centre	
Nithin	Amirth Jayasree	Brunel Composites Centre	
Dimitris	Anastasiou	ENTELEA LTD	
Andrea	Minigher	AEP Polymers s.r.l.	
Marco	Monti	Proplast	
Ilaria	Poncini	Proplast	
Sonia	Gandini	Proplast	
Susana	Remotti	Proplast	
Marta	Zaccone	Proplast	

M6 General Assembly Meeting

04th December 2024

Brunel Composites Centre, Cambridge

Participant list

Name	Surname	Company	Signature
Ural	HALACIOGLU	ZORLU ENERJİ	
Zeynep	KORKMAZ	ZORLU ENERJİ	
MARCO	MONTI	PROPLAST	
MIREN	BLANCO	TEKNIKER	
Marco	Comzana	Poli Mi	
Riccardo	Di Giovanni	Poli Mi	
KARLA	RONENI	PROPLAST	
SONIA	GANDINI	PROPLAST	
CRISTINA	MONTESERIN	TEKNIKER	
XABIER	MUNOZAVE	NORVENTO	
DIMITRIOS	ANASTASIOU	ENTELEA LTD	
Mando	Kostapanou	IRES	
Georgios	Karamulidis	IRES	
Walter	Pitacco	AEP POLYESTERS	
Daniel	Paul	BCC	
Cecilia	Vizquez	NORVENTO ENERGIA	
Viktor	Tony & Co	BCC	

M6 General Assembly Meeting

05th December 2024

Brunel Composites Centre, Cambridge

Participant list

Name	Surname	Company	Signature
SONIA	GANDINI	PROPLAST	
ILARIA	PONCINI	PROPLAST	
MARCO	MONTI	PROPLAST	
WALTER	PITACCO	AEP POLYMERS	
Marco	CONDONO	POLIMI	
RICCARDO	DI GIOVANNI	POLIMI	
URAL	HALILOGLU	ZORLU ENERJİ	
Zeynep	KORKMAZ	ZORLU ENERJİ	
Claudia	Vázquez	NORVENTO ENERGIA	
DIMITRIOS	ANASTASIOU	ENTELEA LTD.	
Daniel	Paul	BCC	
Mando	Kostapanou	IREG	
Georgios	Kourouklidis	IREG	
977226	79007	EGEG	
Nythin	Touadour	BCC	
MILLEN	BLANCO	TEKNIKER	
CRISTINA	MONTESERIN	TEKNIKER	

M12 General Assembly Meeting 16th June 2025 Tekniker, Bilbao

Participant list

Name	Surname	Company	Signature
ILARIA	PONCINI	PROPLAST	
DANIEL	PAUL	Brunei University	
XABIER	MUNDUATE	NORVENTO	
VIKTOR	VIKOR	ESC. 7	
GEORGIOS	KOUROUKLIDIS	IRES	
ADALANTIA	KOSKAPALDY	IRES	
IRAL	MALAYOGLU	ZORLU ENERJİ	
ROBERTO	FRASSINE	EUCIA	
ALESSANDRO	MILITE	POLIMI	
MARCO	LOPCANA	Pol. It.	
RICCARDO	DI GIOVANNI	POLIMI	
ALAZNE	MARTINEZ	TEKNIKER	
IRAIDE	ONAINDIA	TEKNIKER	
WALTER	PITACCO	AEP POLYOTERS	
ANDREA	MINIGHIER	AEP POLYOTERS	
MARCO	MONTI	PROPLAST	
MIREN	BLANCO	TEKNIKER	
CRISTINA	MONTESERIN	TEKNIKER	

M12 General Assembly Meeting 17th June 2025 Tekniker, Bilbao

Participant list

Name	Surname	Company	Signature
SONIA	GANDINI	PROPLAST	
SUSANNA	REMOTTI	PROPLAST	
IACIA	POWELI	PROPLAST	
WALTER	PITACCO	AEP POLYMERS	
ANDREA	MINIGHIER	AEP POLYMERS	
DANIEL	PAUL	Brunel	
YVES	YCOB	ESCIA	
XABIER	MUNDURATE	NORVENTO	
PABLO	NOEVER	NORVENTO	
GEORGIOI	KOUROUKLIDIS	IRES	
ADAMANTIA	KOSTAPANOU	IRES	
Ural	HALACIOLU	ZOTIU ENERJI	
Zeynep	KORKMAZ	ZOTIU ENERJI	
ALESSANDRO	MILITE	POLIMI	
MARCO L.	LUNGANA	Pol. IT.	
RICCARDO	DI GIOVANNI	POLIMI	
ALAINE	MARINETT	TEK	
IRAIDE	ONAINDA	TEK	
CRISTINA	MONTESERIN	TEKNIKER	
MIREN	BLANCO	TEKNIKER	
MARCO	MONTI	PROPLAST	

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or CINEA. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement no. 101147532.